

**METHODS OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC
RHINITIS, HYPERTROPHIC AND ATROPHIC RHINITIS**

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Relevance of the topic: Allergic rhinitis is a disease of the upper respiratory tract, which occurs due to the occurrence of an allergic reaction in the body. This disease is often seasonal (if there is an allergy to pollen). Rhinitis can be acute or chronic.

Purpose of work: Rhinitis occurs due to swelling of the mucous membrane of the nose. The main causes of the disease are allergens, the most common of which are plant pollinators, dust, pet dander, chemicals, drugs, and fungi.

This disease is passed from generation to generation. In children, this disease occurs due to weakened immunity.

1. Symptoms of allergic rhinitis
2. Allergic rhinitis is characterized by the following symptoms:
3. flu;
4. runny nose;
5. frequent sneezing;
6. tickling sensation in the throat;
7. continuous coughing attacks;
8. itchy eyes, increased tearing;
9. increased sensitivity of eyes to light;
10. loss of sense of smell;

11. If you find that you have similar symptoms, contact your doctor immediately. It is easier to prevent the consequences of the disease than to eliminate it.

Diagnostics

To determine the method of treatment, the allergist-doctor, after conducting a general examination and listening to the patient's complaint, prescribes the following tests and analyses:

- general analysis of blood;
- immunogram;
- laboratory examination of mucus secreted from the nose;
- rhinoscopy;
- provocative skin tests to determine the cause of allergies.
- Treatment of allergic rhinitis
- Treatment of allergic rhinitis includes:
 - immunotherapy;
 - antihistamine drugs;
 - vasoconstrictor drugs;
 - cell membrane stabilizers;
 - glucocorticosteroids;
 - therapeutic exercises;
 - inhalation.

In case of chronic rhinitis caused by the curvature of the nasal septum, surgery is prescribed.

During the treatment of the disease, the doctor prescribes a certain diet to the patient, which excludes the following foods:

chicken meat, chicken eggs;
fruits (especially citrus fruits);
honey and related products;
foods and liquids with dyes and food additives.

Dangerous aspects

Conclusion: Avoid contact with allergens;
restriction of movement in the open air in the summer (if there is an allergy to plant dust);
perform wet cleaning at home at least once a week;
before using shampoos, bath gels, creams and other cosmetics, try applying them to the bend of the elbow to check for an allergic reaction;
proper nutrition.

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